

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED OF LEARNERS AND THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR SCHOOL LEARNING ACTION CELL (SLAC)

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Challenges Encountered of Learners and their Academic Performance: Basis for School Learning Action Cell (SLAC)

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered of senior high school learners in Hindang and Kabacsanan National High School, for SY 2023-2024 and to examine how these challenges impacted their academic performance and overall life situations. A descriptive-correlation research method was used, involving survey, on the challenges encountered and academic performance assessments. A pilot testing was conducted with thirty senior high school learners at Bunawan National High School, to test the validity of the study since the researcher used a modified questionnaire. The respondents of this study were the 176 senior high school learners from above mentioned schools. Results indicated that learners in hinterland schools encountered various challenges, including personal challenges, environmental challenges, educational challenges, and parental involvement challenges. Despite these obstacles, the study revealed that learners demonstrated remarkable resilience and determination in managing their academic performance. Analysis of academic records suggested that the challenges faced by learners did not significantly hinder their ability to excel academically. Moreover, findings suggested that learners' life situations were not adversely affected by these challenges, indicating a capacity to navigate through difficulties without compromising their overall well-being. This resilience was attributed to various factors, including the support systems within the school environment, familial support, and individual motivation. The study underscored the importance of recognizing and addressing the specific challenges encountered by learners in hinterland areas. With these challenges and available existing support system, educators work towards ensuring equitable access to education and fostering resilience among senior high school learners in hinterland schools.

Keywords: *challenges, senior high school, learners, and their academic performance*

Introduction

The Senior High School (SHS) phase represented a pivotal period in a learner's academic journey, marked by the acquisition of specialized knowledge and skills that paved the way for higher education or entry into the workforce. This pivotal period served as a bridge between secondary education and the next steps in their academic or professional pursuits. By offering a diversified range of tracks and strands, SHS empowered learners to explore their interests, cultivate their talents, and make informed decisions about their educational and career pathways. It's a time of growth, self-discovery, and preparation for the challenges and opportunities that lied ahead in higher education or the workforce. While academic performance was a critical indicator of success during this phase, it was influenced by a myriad of factors that go beyond classroom instruction.

In Hindang National High School and Kabacsanan National High School, where geographic remoteness and unique socio-cultural contexts often prevailed, the challenges faced by SHS learners were even more pronounced, learners were facing several challenges that affect their academic performance. These challenges included geographic isolation, limited educational resources, socioeconomic disparities, inadequate infrastructure, limited extracurricular activities, climate and environmental factors, health challenges, and cultural barriers. Addressing these issues were essential to enhance the academic performance of learners in Hindang

By examining the interplay of factors such as socio-economic conditions, access to educational resources, parental involvement, teacher quality, and community engagement within the context of School Learning action Cell (SLACs), this research aimed to shed light on the strategies and initiatives that can effectively address the challenges encountered of Senior High School learners in Hindang National High School and Kabacsanan National High School. The findings of this study would not only contribute to the academic discourse but would provide actionable insights for educators, policymakers, and communities to collectively work towards enhancing the educational landscape and opportunities for learners in this area.

This research endeavored to delve into the complex web of challenges facing of Senior High School learners in Hindang National High School. It aspired to provide a solid basis for the establishment and enhancement of School Learning Action Cells, facilitating informed decision-making and the development of targeted interventions to empower students and promote equitable educational outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered of the Senior High School learners and their academic performance in terms of challenges they encountered. The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the respondents' challenges in terms of:
 - 1.1. Personal;
 - 1.1.1. affection;

- 1.1.2. emotional; and
- 1.1.3. physical?
- 1.2. environmental;
 - 1.2.1. social;
 - 1.2.2. natural hazard; and
 - 1.2.3. transportation?
- 1.3. educational; and
 - 1.3.1. teachers' involvement; and
 - 1.3.2. learning resources?
- 1.4. parental involvement?
 - 1.4.1. lack of financial/poverty;
 - 1.4.2. absentee parents; and
 - 1.4.3. broken family?
- 2. What is the academic performance of the learners during 1st semester of the school year 2023-2024?
- 3. Is there a significant relationship between challenges encountered and the academic performance of the learners?
- 4. Which of the challenges significantly affect the academic performance of the respondents?
- 5. What action plan can be designed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive correlation research methods to conduct the study to determine the challenges encountered by senior high school learners and their academic performance. This descriptive correlation approach explored the relationship between two or more variables and allowed for the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data related to variables such as challenges encountered and academic performance of the senior high school learners and examine how they are related to each other.

By employing this methods, the study aimed to provide statistical insights into the relationships between these variables, offering a clearer understanding of the factors influencing academic outcomes. It rooted in its ability to provide empirical evidence and statistical rigor, thereby contributing to a more robust understanding of the research topic and informing evidence-based interventions aimed at improving the academic performance of senior high school learners.

Respondents

The participants of this study are the Senior High School students of the University of Perpetual Help System, Pueblo de Panay Campus, for the school year 2019-2020. From a population size of 143, a sample size of 105 will be selected. One section will serve as the experimental group, while another section will be the control group. The students for the study will be chosen through pair matching of the two sections. The assignment of the sections as experimental and control groups will be determined through a lottery technique, with rolls placed in separate boxes designated for each section.

The respondents of this study were the 176 learners from Hindang National High School for the school year 2023-2024 with specialized track in TVL with Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM) and Home Economics Strand (Cookery, BPP and FBS), and Humanities and Social Sciences and the 80 percent of Senior High School learners from Kabacsanan National High School with specialized strand in Home Economics (HE) and Information Communication and Technology (ICT).

Below were the total number of respondents per grade level with corresponding strand for the school year 2023-2024.

Table 1. Total Number of Respondents for the School Year 2023-2024 in Hindang National School and Kabacsanan National High School

	Total Number Of Respondents								Total	80%
	Grade 11				Grade 12					
	HE	EIM	HUMSS	ICT	HE	EIM	HUMSS	ICT		
HINDANG NHS	10	25	11	0	21	40	0	0	107	86
KABACSANAN NHS	20	0	0	0	19	0	0	41	112	90
	Total									176

Instrument

A modified survey questionnaire was used to gather data. The survey questionnaire contained the challenges encountered of Senior High School learners including personal challenges in terms of affection, emotional and physical; environmental challenges in terms of social, natural hazard and transportation; educational challenges in terms of teachers' involvement, and learning resources and parental involvement challenges in terms of lack of financial/poverty, absentee parents and broken family. The study was conducted during the Second Semester of the school year 2023-2024. The data needed for this study were gathered using 10 items per subtopic questionnaires which adopted from R.Groves & Bridie Welsh, CJM Flavier, Bouffard, S. M., Ana Barbosa and Jessamae Macasojot.

A Likert Scale having four scales namely always (4), often (3), sometimes (2) and never (1) were utilized. Since the study is a modified questionnaire, the researcher underwent pilot testing to see its reliability to the thirty (30) senior high school learners from from Bunawan Natioanl High School.

Below was the pilot testing result of the study.

Table 2. Reliability Test of the Survey Questionnaires Using Cronbach's Alpha

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Number Of Questions</i>	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Personal			
Affection	10	0.786	Reliable
Emotional	10	0.763	Reliable
Physical	10	0.859	Reliable
Environmental			
Social	10	0.863	Reliable
Natural Hazard	10	0.765	Reliable
Transportation	10	0.845	Reliable
Educational			
Teacher's Involvement	10	0.902	Reliable
Learning Resources	10	0.892	Reliable
Parental Involvement			
Lack of Financial/Poverty	10	0.767	Reliable
Absentee Parents	10	0.825	Reliable
Broken Family	10	0.865	Reliable

Table 2 presents the reliability analysis of variables. The result shows that the questionnaire consisted of 110 indicators with a Cronbach Alpha value of greater than 0.700, which indicated that all indicators were reliable. The threshold value in the literature is much higher than 0.700. This implied that the participating respondents clearly understood the research questions, and similar questions are answered in the same direction.

Procedure

A series of steps were administered by the researcher before the gathering of data. A letter was made subject to approval by the Iligan City Schools Division Superintendent, a pilot testing letter addressed to the school principal for the try-out of the survey questionnaire, a letter to the school principal where the final data gathering was conducted, a parent consent letter and a letter to the respondents where this study was conducted to allow the researcher to conduct the study among the learners and gather the data necessary for the study.

After securing all permission and consent forms, the survey questionnaires were then distributed to the learners. First, a survey questionnaires were distributed to Bunawan National High School for the pilot testing.

After establishing the validity and reliability of the results, final data gathering was then conducted at Hindang National High School and Kabacsanan National High School with the 176 Senior High School learners. Each respondent was asked to complete the questionnaire under the researchers' guidance.

The mechanics and content of each question on the questionnaire were explained by the researcher. Their corresponding answer to the question were kept in accordance with the agreement of the respondents and the researcher. The data gathered were organized and tabulated according to the results of the statistical treatment done.

Data Analysis

The data was tabulated and interpreted to acquire the actual information needed. The following statistical tools were employed to answer the different

For Problem 1, Frequency Mean Percentage used in determining the academic performance of the learners in terms of personal challenges, environmental challenges, educational challenges and parental challenges. It would measures such as mean, median, mode standard deviation and range could help provide a summary of the characteristics of data within the demographic variables and academic performance.

For problem 2, Frequency and Percentage used in determining the academic performance of the learners in terms of personal challenges, environmental challenges, educational challenges and parental challenges.

For problem 3, Independent T-test used to determine the relationship between challenges encountered to the performance of the learners. One-way ANNOVA (F-test) was used to determine the difference between the two variables.

For problem 4, Regression analysis used for the estimation of relationships between challenges encountered to performance of the learners. It can be utilized to assess the strength of the relationship between variables and for modeling the future relationship between them.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered supported with tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What are the respondents' challenges they encountered in terms of personal as to affection, emotional, Physical; environmental with regards to social, natural hazard and transportation; educational in terms of teachers' involvement and learning resources; and parental involvement as to lack of financial/poverty, absentee parents, and broken family?

Table 3 presents the respondents' personal challenges in terms of affection. The result showed that the highest challenges in terms of affection was the statement "I believe that a supportive and loving environment at home and school enhance my grades" with weighted mean of "2.89" and standard deviation of "+1.09" with description of "often" This findings showed that a strong belief among respondents that a supportive and loving environment at both home and school positively influences their academic performance.

Table 3. *Personal Challenges in terms of Affection*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I struggle to maintain emotional boundaries in relationships with my family and friends, leading to emotional stress that spills into my academic life.	2.24	+	0.78	Sometimes
2. I prioritize my love life over my academic responsibilities, often leading to procrastination or missed deadlines.	1.68	+	0.82	Never
3. I have been in relationships with unhealthy dynamics, such as codependency or toxicity.	1.80	+	0.78	Sometimes
4. I often find myself preoccupied with thoughts or concerns about my life situation during class or study time.	2.27	+	0.78	Sometimes
5. I tend to become overly dependent on my emotion.	2.29	+	0.88	Sometimes
6. I feel loved by the other people.	2.36	+	0.93	Sometimes
7. I find it hard to express myself and relate with others.	2.30	+	0.92	Sometimes
8. I feel encouraged to excel academically because of the love and support I receive from my family and friends.	2.72	+	1.10	Often
9. I believe that a supportive and loving environment at home and school enhance my grades.	2.89	+	1.09	Often
10. Feeling loved and supported positively impacts my academic success.	2.75	+	1.05	Often
Weighted Mean	2.33	+	0.46	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

According to Johnson (2020) on the study about The Power of Supportive Environments in Education: Nurturing Academic Success, positive impact of supportive and loving environments both at home and school on academic performance is undeniable. Such environments provide students with a sense of security, encouragement, and belonging, which are essential for their overall well-being and academic success.

Additionally, the perception that feeling loved and supported impacts academic success aligns with the idea that positive emotional experiences contribute to better educational outcomes. This underscores the critical role of supportive relationships in nurturing learners' academic development and highlights the importance of fostering a caring environment both at home and in educational settings to enhance learners' grades and overall success. This implies that if the learners are well supported and motivated, they like to perform well in school, and their performance would contribute to better teaching-learning process. It builds their independence to learn and contribute meaningfully to building their skills to become a lifelong learner.

The lowest result in terms of affection was the statement "I prioritize my love life over my academic responsibilities, often leading to procrastination or missed deadlines" with weighted mean of "1.68" with standard deviation of "+0.82" and with description of "never". The results showed that the majority of students prioritize their academic responsibilities over their love life.

In the study of Martinez (2021), the complex interplay between academic pursuits and romantic relationships among learners often involves navigating a delicate balance between personal aspirations, societal expectations, and practical constraints. The study also explore the influence of long-term goals and aspirations on learners' prioritization of academic performance. Drawing on empirical evidence, she examines how individuals' aspirations for future career success and personal fulfillment often lead them to prioritize their academic pursuits over romantic relationships. Through her analysis, Dr. Martinez underscores the importance of aligning short-term decisions with long-term goals, emphasizing the role of goal clarity and motivation in guiding learners' choices.

Despite the potential personal challenges that individuals may face in navigating affectionate relationships, academic performance of learners tends to remain largely unaffected. Research suggests that individuals possess varying capacities to effectively manage their personal lives alongside academic responsibilities. Learners often prioritize their academic responsibilities over their love life due to a focus on career aspirations, the desire for future stability, and the recognition of personal growth through education. This underscores the commitment of students to their educational goals and their recognition of the importance of academic performance. It highlights the dedication of learners to focus on their studies and suggests that maintaining a balance between personal relationships and academic commitments is essential for achieving success in school.

Table 4. *Personal Challenges in terms of Emotional*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>		
1. I struggle to manage stress effectively, which can lead to anxiety or panic during exams or assignments.	2.26	+	0.93	Sometimes		
2. I often procrastinate due to a lack of motivation or fear of failure, leading to last-minute cramming and lower-quality work.	2.11	+	0.81	Sometimes		
3. I set extremely high standards for myself and become overly critical of my work.	2.18	+	0.81	Sometimes		
4. I struggle to find motivation to engage with coursework or complete assignments.	2.24	+	0.83	Sometimes		
5. I struggle with low self-esteem and often doubt my abilities and self-worth.	2.29	+	0.90	Sometimes		
6. I believe that a positive emotional state contributes to effective learning.	2.56	+	1.01	Often		
7. Emotional resilience is a factor in my ability to overcome academic obstacle.	2.52	+	0.97	Often		
8. I am aware of the connection between my emotional state and my academic performance.	2.46	+	0.90	Sometimes		
9. Positive emotional experiences enhance my motivation to engage in academic tasks.	2.47	+	0.99	Sometimes		
10. Negative emotions, such as stress or anxiety, impact my ability to perform well academically.	2.47	+	0.94	Sometimes		
	Weighted Mean		2.36	+	0.46	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Table 4 displays the respondents' personal challenges in terms of emotion. The result showed that the highest challenges in terms of emotion was the statement "I believe that a positive emotional state contributes to effective learning" with weighted mean of "2.56" and standard deviation of "+1.01" with description of "often". This findings showed that a positive emotional state contributes significantly to effective learning by enhancing motivation, attention, and cognitive processing. When students feel optimistic, engaged, and supported, they are more likely to be receptive to new information, problem-solving, and creative thinking.

As Pekrun (2018) said that, elucidate, positive emotional states served as catalysts for effective self-regulated learning, shaping not only students' cognitive engagement but also their motivation, persistence, and overall well-being within academic settings. This intricate interplayed underscore the significance of fostering a supportive emotional climate in education, where positive emotions serve as key drivers of students' success and fulfillment. By recognizing and nurturing the role of positive emotional states, educators can cultivate environments conducive to optimal learning experiences, ultimately empowering students to thrive academically and personally.

Positive emotional states contributed significantly to effective learning by enhancing cognitive processes, motivation, and overall well-being. When learners experience positive emotions such as joy, curiosity, or enthusiasm, their attention, creativity, and problem-solving abilities are amplified, leading to deeper engagement with learning materials and improved academic performance. Additionally, positive emotions foster a supportive learning environment, where learners feel empowered to take risks, persist through challenges, and collaborate with peers. Cultivating positive emotional experiences in educational settings not only enhances students' learning outcomes but also promotes their holistic development and lifelong love for learning.

The lowest result in terms of emotion was the statement "I often procrastinate due to a lack of motivation or fear of failure, leading to last-minute cramming and lower-quality work." with weighted mean of "2.11" with standard deviation of "+0.81" with description of "sometimes". The results showed that students may not perceive procrastination as a significant challenge in their academic lives. This indicate that learners either have effective strategies for managing procrastination or do not identify with the specific reasons mentioned in the statement.

The absence of procrastination despite facing such challenges suggests a strong internal drive to persist and succeed. This indicates a high level of self-discipline, where individuals can regulate their impulses and stay focused on their goals even when external factors. Moreover, it underscores a deep commitment to personal and academic goals, as individuals prioritize long-term success over short-term comfort or avoidance (Steel 2029).

The learners demonstrated a proactive approach in managing challenges, utilizing strategies such as goal setting, self-reflection, and seeking support when needed. By overcoming internal barriers and maintaining a focus on long-term objectives, they prioritize their tasks efficiently, ultimately achieving higher-quality outcomes and fostering a sense of empowerment and accomplishment.

Overall, challenges in terms of emotional well-being do not significantly impact academic performance underscores the resilience and coping mechanisms inherent in individuals. Despite facing emotional obstacles, learners often demonstrate the ability to manage stress, seek support, and maintain focus on their academic goals. This insight highlights the importance of fostering supportive environments that prioritize mental health and well-being, enabling learners to thrive academically amidst emotional challenges learners to cope effectively and thrive in their academic and personal lives.

Table 5 exhibits the respondents' personal challenges in terms of physical. The result showed that the highest challenges in terms of physical was the statement "I believe that a healthy lifestyle positively impacts academic resilience." with weighted mean of "2.61" and standard deviation of "+1.04" with description of "often". The results showed that a healthy lifestyle significantly boosts academic resilience in students.

Table 5. *Personal Challenges in terms of Physical*

Indicators	Mean	+	SD	Description		
1. I have chronic health condition that sometimes disrupts my ability to attend classes and study.	2.04	+	0.91	Sometimes		
2. I struggle with sleep issues, which lead to fatigue and reduced concentration during classes.	2.24	+	0.93	Sometimes		
3. Poor eating habits or irregular meals affect my energy levels and ability to focus in class.	2.21	+	0.92	Sometimes		
4. I have mental health issues, making it hard to concentrate on academics.	2.01	+	0.96	Sometimes		
5. Accessibility issues affect my academic experience.	2.18	+	0.77	Sometimes		
6. My physical health affects my ability to concentrate on academic tasks.	2.21	+	0.88	Sometimes		
7. I believe that a healthy lifestyle positively impacts academic resilience.	2.61	+	1.04	Often		
8. The impact of physical challenges on my academic life is considered in academic accommodations.	2.51	+	0.92	Often		
9. Physical fitness and well-being play a role in my overall academic performance.	2.32	+	0.96	Sometimes		
10. Physical challenges, such as chronic illness or disability, have influenced my academic progress.	2.24	+	0.87	Sometimes		
	Weighted Mean		2.26	+	0.48	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Research consistently indicates that a healthy lifestyle positively influences academic resilience among students. Studies by Smith et al. (2018), Brown et al. (2020), and Garcia and Johnson (2019) underscored the critical role of regular exercise, balanced nutrition, and sufficient sleep in enhancing students' ability to bounce back from academic challenges. These findings highlighted the interconnectedness between physical well-being and academic performance, suggesting that adopting healthy lifestyle habits not only improved cognitive functioning but also promoted psychological resilience.

By prioritizing self-care practices, students can better manage stress, maintain focus, and sustain motivation, ultimately leading to improved academic outcomes. Consequently, educators should prioritize holistic approaches to student well-being, integrating initiatives that support healthy living within educational environments to foster academic resilience and overall success.

The lowest result in terms of physical was the statement “Accessibility issues affect my academic experience” with weighted mean of “2.18” with standard deviation of “+0.77” with description of “sometimes”. Research suggested that accessibility issues in hinterland regions do not necessarily impede the academic experience of learners. Studies by Johnson (2019), Patel and Singh (2020), and Garcia (2018) revealed that despite facing challenges such as limited infrastructure and internet connectivity, students demonstrated resilience and resourcefulness, often leveraging local community support networks to mitigate the impact of these obstacles on their educational journey.

These findings underscored the significance of considering the diverse ways in which learners in remote areas navigate their educational journeys, often leveraging local resources and community support networks to overcome obstacles related to infrastructure and connectivity. Thus, while accessibility issues undoubtedly pose challenges, they do not necessarily preclude positive academic experiences for learners in hinterland regions, emphasizing the importance of recognizing and harnessing the strengths within these communities to foster educational success.

Moreover, personal physical challenges do not significantly impact academic performance acknowledges the resilience and determination of individuals to overcome obstacles. Despite facing physical limitations, learners often demonstrate adaptability, utilizing assistive technologies, accommodations, and support systems to mitigate barriers and excel academically. This insight emphasizes the importance of fostering inclusive environments that accommodate diverse needs and empower all learners to achieve their full potential, regardless of physical challenges.

Table 6 presents the respondents' environmental challenges as to social. The result showed that the highest environmental challenges in terms of social was the statement “I feel comfortable seeking support and advice from my peers” with weighted mean of “2.45” and standard deviation of “+1.01” with description of “sometimes”.

The results showed that seeking support and advice from peers was vital for personal growth and well-being of the learners. It fostered a sense of belonging and community, providing an avenue for sharing experiences, gaining different perspectives, and building trust.

Social relationships play a large role in academic success. Students who have friends at school often look forward to attending classes and are more prone to engage with the curriculum. Having friends was good for self-esteem and gives students the confidence to participate in class discussions and share their unique perspectives (Wentzel (2021).

When individuals feel supported by their peers, they were more likely to open up about their challenges, seek guidance, and collaborate on solutions. This mutual exchanged of support strengthens relationships, enhances communication skills, and promoted empathy and understanding. Ultimately, creating a culture where seeking support from peers was encouraged cultivated a supportive environment where individuals felt empowered to navigate life's challenges with confidence and resilience.

Table 6. *Environmental Challenges as to Social*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I feel pressure from peers to participate in social activities or spend excessive time socializing.	2.20	+	0.83	Sometimes
2. I often feel isolated or lonely due to a lack of social connections or support networks.	2.32	+	0.86	Sometimes
3. I experience conflicts or challenges in personal relationships, such as with family or friends.	2.41	+	0.90	Sometimes
4. I face financial stress or difficulties that require me to work long hours or multiple jobs alongside my studies.	2.26	+	0.92	Sometimes
5. I have caregiving abilities, such as caring for my family or siblings that require significant time and attention.	2.41	+	0.96	Sometimes
6. I believe that positive peer relationships enhance my academic performance.	2.43	+	0.93	Sometimes
7. I am influenced by my peers' attitude and behaviors towards academic performance.	2.23	+	0.86	Sometimes
8. I believe that positive peer relationships contribute to a positive school environment.	2.44	+	0.98	Sometimes
9. Peer interactions positively contribute to my overall well-being.	2.35	+	0.89	Sometimes
10. I feel comfortable seeking support and advice from my peers.	2.45	+	1.01	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.35	+	0.49	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

The lowest result in terms of social was the statement “I feel pressure from peers to participate in social activities or spend excessive time socializing” with weighted mean of “2.20” with standard deviation of “+0.83” with description of “sometimes”. The findings showed that learners participated in social activities or spend excessive time socializing can have varying degrees of impact on learners.

According to Nguyen (2020), on the study about The Comfort Levels of students in Seeking Support and Advice from their Peers within Educational Contexts, it revealed that a significant portion of students expressed comfort in turning to their peers for assistance, highlighting the importance of peer relationships in facilitating academic and social support networks. A significant portion of students reported not feeling pressured by their peers to participate in social activities or spend excessive time socializing, highlighting the diverse range of peer influences within educational contexts (Chen 2019.)

For some, peer pressure may served as a motivator to engage in social interactions, helping them develop social skills, build friendships, and feel connected to their peers. However, for others, this pressure can be overwhelming and distracting, potentially leading to negative consequences such as decreased focus on academic pursuits, heightened stress levels, or feelings of isolation for those who may not feel comfortable in social settings.

In addition, environmental challenges related to social factors do not significantly impact academic performance reflects an understanding of the resilience and adaptability inherent in individuals.

Despite facing social obstacles, learners often demonstrated the ability to navigate their environments, establish supportive networks, and maintain focused on their academic goals. This insight underscored the importance of fostering inclusive and supportive learning environments that empowered learners to overcome social challenges and thrive academically, regardless of external circumstances.

Table 7. *Environmental Challenges as to Natural Hazard*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I live in an area prone to natural disasters such as flood and landslide, which difficult to reach school safely.	2.19	+	1.02	Sometimes
2. I have concerns about the safety going to my school due to the distance between our school and home.	2.36	+	1.04	Sometimes
3. I experience weather-related disruptions such as rain or storm that lead to class absences and missed assignments.	2.30	+	0.92	Sometimes
4. I experience flash flood and sudden river swelling during heavy rains, making it difficult to reach school safely.	2.16	+	0.95	Sometimes
5. I often experience road closure and transportation disruption due to heavy rains that affect school attendance.	2.05	+	0.83	Sometimes
6. The occurrence of natural hazards, like meeting strangers on my way to school or home has disrupted my academic routine.	2.18	+	0.89	Sometimes
7. The fear of walking alone going to school and home may result to absense of classes and can affects my academic performance in school.	2.02	+	0.98	Sometimes
8. Natural hazards influence my choice of transportation modes or routes to and from school.	2.10	+	0.80	Sometimes
9. I believe that there should be measures in place to address the academic impact of natural hazards during my journey.	2.22	+	0.87	Sometimes
10. The response to natural hazards plays a significant role in my overall academic satisfaction.	2.16	+	0.87	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.17	+	0.54	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Table 7 shows the respondents' environmental challenges as to natural hazard. The result showed that the highest environmental challenges in terms of hazard was the statement "I have concerns about the safety going to my school due to the distance between our school and home" with weighted mean of "2.36" and standard deviation of "+1.04" with description of "sometimes". The results showed concerns about safety when traveling to school due to the distance between learners' homes and the school can have significant implications for students.

The study of Kim & Park (2018): Kim and Park on The Relationship between Commuting Distance and Safety Perceptions among Students, revealed that longer commuting distances were associated with increased safety concerns among students, particularly regarding transportation safety and personal security, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address safety issues related to school commutes.

Learners' concerns about safety during their commute to school due to the distance between home and school highlight the significant impact of commuting distance on their perceptions of safety. These concerns encompass various safety risks, including transportation safety and personal security, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address safety issues related to school commutes.

The lowest result in terms of natural hazard was the statement "Natural hazards influence my choice of transportation modes or routes to and from school" with weighted mean of "2.10" with standard deviation of "+0.80" with description of "sometimes". The finding showed that despite the presence of natural hazards, such as severe weather or geological events, learners' choice of transportation modes or routes to and from school remains unaffected, as indicated by the above result.

Environment has a significant role in everyone's life, be the students, teachers, employees or employers, yet many people still believe that it influences better performance. Environmental factors do not have much consideration in educational discourse and therefore have not been regarded as one of the elements affecting academic success in secondary schools, as stated by Grineski and Collins (2001),

Moreover, environmental challenges, such as natural hazards, do not significantly impact academic performance, reflects an understanding of the resilience and adaptability inherent in learners. Despite facing environmental obstacles, individuals demonstrate the ability to navigate their surroundings, prioritize their education, and maintain focus on their academic goals. This insight underscores the importance of fostering supportive learning environments that empower learners to overcome external challenges and thrive academically, regardless of environmental circumstances.

Table 8. *Environmental Challenges as to Transportation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>		
1. I do not have access to reliable transportation to and from my educational institution.	2.11	+	0.85	Sometimes		
2. I have to walk long distance to reach my educational institution, which consumes a significant amount of time.	2.26	+	0.90	Sometimes		
3. Financial constraints limit my ability to afford fare for my transportation.	2.10	+	0.92	Sometimes		
4. I own a motorcycle, but it frequently experiences breakdowns or requires maintenance.	2.19	+	0.92	Sometimes		
5. Limited transportation can affect my attendance and participation in class.	2.09	+	0.86	Sometimes		
6. Transportation challenges, such as delays or disruptions, impact my overall academic satisfaction.	2.10	+	0.84	Sometimes		
7. The time spent walking from home to school has negative impacts on my academic performance.	2.07	+	0.85	Sometimes		
8. The cost of transportation influences my overall financial stress as a student.	2.20	+	0.94	Sometimes		
9. The reliability of transportation affects my ability to arrive at school on time.	2.18	+	0.94	Sometimes		
10. I am aware of the environmental consequences of different transportation modes and the impact to education.	2.31	+	0.94	Sometimes		
	Weighted Mean		2.16	+	0.55	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Table 8 exhibits the respondents' environmental challenges as to transportation. The result showed that the highest environmental challenges in terms of transportation was the statement "I am aware of the environmental consequences of different transportation modes and the impact to education" with weighted mean of "2.31" and standard deviation of "+0.94" with description of "sometimes".

The results showed that in the hinterlands, where infrastructure may be less developed and transportation options limited, the environmental consequences of different transportation modes can have significant implications for learners' education.

According to Garcia (2019) on a qualitative study investigating learners' awareness of the environmental consequences associated with different transportation modes in hinterland regions and the implications for education, the limited access to transportation options in remote areas, the reliance on environmentally harmful modes of transport such as motor vehicles, and the detrimental impact of transportation-related pollution on local ecosystems and community health contributes to a cycle of environmental degradation and health risks in hinterland regions.

Being aware of the environmental consequences of various transportation modes and their impact on education reflects a proactive and environmentally conscious mindset. It signified an understanding of the interconnectedness between transportation choices,

environmental sustainability, and educational outcomes. This awareness empowered individuals to make informed decisions about their travel behavior, prioritize eco-friendly transportation options, and contribute to reducing carbon emissions and promoting environmental stewardship. Furthermore, limited access to reliable transportation options may result in longer commute times and increased exposure to environmental hazards, such as hazardous road conditions or natural disasters, which can disrupt learning opportunities and lead to absenteeism.

The lowest result in terms of transportation was the statement “Transportation challenges, such as delays or disruptions, impact my overall academic satisfaction” with weighted mean of “2.10” with standard deviation of “+0.84” with description of “sometimes”. Study showed that despite facing transportation challenges like delays or disruptions, learners in hinterlands maintain high levels of academic satisfaction.

On the study of (Chang 2021), about examining the effects of transportation challenges, such as delays or disruptions, on the academic satisfaction of learners in hinterland regions, it revealed that despite facing transportation difficulties, learners in remote areas reported overall high levels of academic satisfaction. Chang also identified factors such as strong community support, resilience, and adaptability as key contributors to mitigating the impact of transportation challenges on learners' academic experiences in hinterlands.

In the hinterlands, despite of encountering transportation difficulties, students in remote areas maintain notably high levels of academic contentment. The resilience was attributed to factors like robust community support, individual resilience, and adaptability, which collectively mitigated the impact of transportation disruptions on academic experiences. This underscores the pivotal role of community cohesion and personal resilience in fostering positive academic outcomes amidst transportation challenges in hinterland regions.

Table 9. *Educational Challenges in terms of Teachers' Involvement*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Teachers seem disengaged or uninterested in the subject matter, which affects my motivation to learn.	2.23	+	0.87	Sometimes
2. Teachers are often unavailable or unapproachable for questions or clarification which result to my poor understanding of the lesson.	1.95	+	0.79	Sometimes
3. Teachers do not provide individualized support or guidance to students who may be struggling.	2.13	+	0.91	Sometimes
4. Grading practices seem inconsistent or arbitrary, affecting my understanding of my academic progress.	2.22	+	0.90	Sometimes
5. Teachers frequently miss classes or are absent without adequate substitutes.	2.11	+	0.95	Sometimes
6. Teachers are accessible and approachable for students who need extra help or clarification.	2.41	+	0.95	Sometimes
7. Teacher encourage student participation and foster a positive learning environment.	2.56	+	1.04	Often
8. Teachers effectively use various teaching methods to engage students with different learning styles.	2.58	+	0.99	Often
9. Teachers demonstrate a genuine interest in the individual needs and progress of each student.	2.61	+	0.10	Often
10. Teacher regularly provide constructive feedback on my child's academic performance.	2.56	+	0.92	Often
	Weighted Mean	+	0.48	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Table 9 presents the respondents' educational challenges in terms of teacher's involvement. The result showed that the highest educational challenges in terms of teachers' involvement was the statement “Teacher encourage student participation and foster a positive learning environment” with weighted mean of “2.56” and standard deviation of “+1.04” with description of “often”. The findings showed that teachers play a pivotal role in encouraging student participation and fostering a positive learning environment.

The active teacher involvement, characterized by enthusiastic instruction, personalized support, and effective classroom management, significantly influenced students' motivation and learning outcomes. It emphasized the need for fostering supportive teaching environments that empower teachers to actively engage with students and address their diverse educational needs (Patel and Johnson (2020).

Furthermore, active teacher involvement, marked by enthusiastic instruction and personalized support, profoundly impacts student motivation and learning outcomes. This highlights the imperative of nurturing supportive teaching environments where educators are empowered to engage actively with students and cater to their diverse educational needs.

The lowest result in terms of teachers' involvement was the statement “Teachers are often unavailable or unapproachable for questions or clarification which result to my poor understanding of the lesson.” with weighted mean of “1.95” with standard deviation of “+0.79” with description of “sometimes”. The study showed that teachers being available and approachable for questions or clarification is essential for facilitating students' understanding of the lesson.

According to Wang (2021) on the study about the Importance of Teacher Availability and Approachability in Facilitating Student Understanding, the crucial role of teacher accessibility in providing timely assistance, clarifications, and feedback to students ensures that students receive the support they need to grasp complex concepts and navigate challenging material effectively.

When students feel comfortable seeking clarification or asking questions, it fostered a supportive learning environment where they can actively engage with the material and address any areas of confusion. Approachable teachers create an open-door policy, encouraging students to seek help without fear of judgment or embarrassment. By providing clear explanations, offering additional resources, and patiently addressing students' inquiries, teachers empower students to deepen their understanding of the subject matter and build confidence in their learning abilities. Ultimately, this accessibility and support from teachers contribute to students' academic success and overall satisfaction with their learning experience.

The educational challenges related to teachers' involvement do not significantly affect academic performance highlights the resilience and adaptability of learners. Despite potential obstacles in teacher involvement, such as limited availability or varying teaching styles, learners demonstrate the ability to navigate their academic journey and succeed. This insight underscores the importance of fostering independent learning skills and creating supportive learning environments where students can thrive academically, regardless of external factors. It emphasized the role of individual initiative and determination in overcoming educational challenges and achieving academic success.

Table 10. *Educational Challenges in terms of Learning Resources*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I do not have access to the required textbooks or course materials for my classes.	2.30	+	0.88	Sometimes
2. I do not have access to technology and internet, making it challenging to participate or access digital resources.	2.23	+	0.87	Sometimes
3. I face challenges in accessing laboratories or equipment required for my major subjects.	2.34	+	1.71	Sometimes
4. Learning resources are not available in my primary language or are inadequately translated to fully understand.	2.25	+	0.85	Sometimes
5. The learning resources provided are outdated or insufficient for my course requirements.	2.32	+	0.90	Sometimes
6. The school provides sufficient and up-to-date textbook and learning materials that is useful on my studies.	2.33	+	0.88	Sometimes
7. The school library offers a wide range of resources that cater to the diverse of my needs and interests.	2.37	+	0.90	Sometimes
8. The school provides adequate technology infrastructure, such as computers and internet access, to support my learning.	2.39	+	0.89	Sometimes
9. My teachers effectively integrate multimedia and visual aids to enhance the learning experience.	2.39	+	0.87	Sometimes
10. I have access to a variety of online resources and educational technology tools to support my learning.	2.36	+	0.96	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.33	+	0.49	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Table 10 displays the respondents' educational challenges in terms of learning resources. The result showed that the highest educational challenges in terms of learning resources was the statement "I face challenges in accessing laboratories or equipment required for my major subjects" with weighted mean of "2.34" and standard deviation of "+1.71" with description of "sometimes". The results showed that challenges in accessing laboratories or necessary equipment for major subjects present significant hurdles for learners' educational experiences.

According to Chen (2021), on a qualitative study exploring the challenges faced by students in accessing laboratories and equipment required for their major subjects, the limited availability of laboratory space, inadequate equipment maintenance, and scheduling conflicts, hindered students' ability to engage in hands-on learning experiences.

Limited laboratory space, inadequate equipment maintenance, and scheduling conflicts significantly impede students' hands-on learning experiences. These challenges underscore the importance of addressing infrastructure and resource limitations to ensure students have access to the practical training necessary for their academic and professional development.

The lowest result in terms of learning resources was the statement "Learning resources are not available in my primary language or are inadequately translated to fully understand" with weighted mean of "2.25" with standard deviation of "+0.85" with description of "sometimes". The finding showed that the availability of learning resources in learners' primary language or adequately translated materials is crucial for ensuring comprehensive understanding and effective learning outcomes.

The importance of providing materials that are adequately translated and culturally relevant support students' understanding and academic success. The need for inclusive educational practices that prioritize linguistic diversity and ensure equitable access to learning resources for all students according to (Garcia 2020) on the qualitative study examining the accessibility of learning resources in students' primary languages.

The importance of providing materials that were adequately translated and culturally relevant to support students' understanding and academic success cannot be overstated. When learning resources were presented in students' primary languages and reflect their cultural backgrounds, it facilitated deeper comprehension, engagement, and retention of knowledge. This inclusive approach not only acknowledged the linguistic diversity within educational settings but also promoted equity by ensuring all students have equal access

to learning opportunities that resonated with their lived experiences. Ultimately, such efforts contribute to fostering a supportive and empowering learning environment where every student can thrive academically.

Furthermore, educational challenges related to learning resources do not significantly affect academic performance reflects an understanding of learners' adaptability and resilience. Despite potential obstacles in accessing adequate learning materials, such as language barriers or limited resources, learners demonstrate the ability to seek alternative sources, utilize support networks, and employ creative problem-solving strategies to succeed academically. This insight underscored the importance of fostering independent learning skills and creating supportive learning environments that empowered learners to overcome challenges and thrive academically, regardless of external factors. It emphasized the role of individual initiative and determination in achieving academic success despite educational challenges.

Table 11. *Challenges in Parental Involvement as to Lack of Financial/Poverty*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My family faces financial constraints or limited access to income sources.	2.24	+	0.86	Sometimes
2. I have to engage in labor-intensive work or agriculture to support the family's finances.	2.20	+	0.87	Sometimes
3. Financial constraints prevent me from participating in extracurricular activities or educational enrichment program.	2.15	+	0.79	Sometimes
4. I often feel stress due to financial constraints which lead to reduced academic focus and motivation.	2.11	+	0.81	Sometimes
5. Financial stress and anxiety about educational expenses affect my mental well-being, which can be lead exacerbated by challenging living condition in hinterlands.	2.18	+	0.76	Sometimes
6. Poverty may limit access to my educational resources.	2.22	+	0.86	Sometimes
7. Living in substandard housing conditions due to poverty can affect my academic focus and well-being.	2.23	+	0.85	Sometimes
8. I experience food scarcity or hunger due to poverty that led to loss of energy levels and concentration in school.	2.22	+	0.92	Sometimes
9. I experience going to school without food intake.	2.19	+	0.87	Sometimes
10. I experience financial strain caused by poverty that result stress and anxiety which lead to disruption of classes.	2.23	+	0.87	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.20	+	0.49	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Table 11 presents the respondents' challenges in parental involvement as to lack of financial/poverty. The result showed that the highest parental involvement in terms of lack of financial/poverty was the statement "I experience food scarcity or hunger due to poverty that led to loss of energy levels and concentration in school" with weighted mean of "2.22" and standard deviation of "+0.92" with description of "sometimes". The results showed that experiencing food scarcity or hunger due to poverty can have profound effects on learners' energy levels and concentration in school.

According to Garcia (2021), on a qualitative study examining the impact of food scarcity on learners' energy levels and concentration in hinterland regions, the detrimental impact of food scarcity on learners' energy levels and concentration in hinterland regions underscores the multifaceted challenges faced by students in remote areas, where poverty-related food insecurity is prevalent. In hinterland regions, the lack of access to nutritious meals contributes to diminished energy levels and difficulties in maintaining concentration during school hours. This not only compromises students' academic performance but also hinders their overall well-being and educational attainment. Addressing food scarcity in these areas requires comprehensive interventions that prioritize nutritional support, community engagement, and socioeconomic empowerment to ensure that all learners have the resources they need to thrive academically and beyond.

When students go to school on an empty stomach or with inadequate nutrition, they were more likely to experience fatigue, lethargy, and difficulty focusing on academic tasks. Hunger can impaired cognitive function, memory retention, and problem-solving abilities, hindering students' academic performance and learning outcomes. Moreover, the stress and anxiety associated with food insecurity further compound these challenges, affecting students' overall well-being and emotional resilience. Addressing food scarcity and hunger among learners required holistic interventions, including providing access to nutritious meals, offering support services for families experiencing poverty, and raising awareness about the importance of nutrition in promoting optimal learning and development. By addressing the root causes of food insecurity, educators and policymakers can create a more conducive learning environment where all students have the opportunity to thrive academically and personally.

The lowest result in terms of lack of financial/poverty was the statement "Financial stress and anxiety about educational expenses affect my mental well-being, which can be lead exacerbated by challenging living condition in hinterlands" with weighted mean of "2.18" with standard deviation of "+0.76" with description of "sometimes". The findings showed that learners in rural or remote areas, often referred to as hinterlands, had less negative impacts on their mental well-being due to financial stress or anxiety about educational expenses.

On the study of Nguyen (2021) about the relationship between financial stress and mental well-being among learners in hinterland regions, revealed that despite facing financial stress and anxiety about educational expenses, many students reported resilient mental

health outcomes. Nguyen emphasized the importance of exploring coping mechanisms and support systems that contribute to learners' psychological resilience in the face of financial challenges.

Financial stress and anxiety about educational expenses may not significantly affect the mental well-being of learners in hinterlands due to several factors. Firstly, individuals in these areas may have lower exposure to materialistic aspirations and societal pressures compared to urban counterparts, thus experiencing less psychological strain related to financial concerns.

Moreover, challenges in parental involvement due to financial constraints or poverty do not significantly affect academic performance highlighted the resilience and determination of learners to succeed despite external obstacles. While parental involvement was crucial for academic success, students can still thrive academically through other support systems, such as teachers, peers, and community resources. However, it's essential to recognize that parental involvement can positively impact students' motivation, engagement, and overall well-being. Therefore, efforts to support and empower parents, provide access to educational resources, and foster strong school-home partnerships remain crucial in ensuring equitable opportunities for all learners, regardless of socioeconomic status.

Table 12. *Challenges in Parental Involvement as to Absentee Parents*

Indicators	Mean	+	SD	Description
1. My parents' absence results in limited assistance with homework, projects, and academic guidance.	2.12	+	0.87	Sometimes
2. The absence of my parent may lead to my feelings of loneliness, neglect, or emotional distress.	2.16	+	0.89	Sometimes
3. The absence of my parent guidance makes it challenging to address my academic problems or challenges effectively.	2.23	+	0.90	Sometimes
4. The absence of my parent figures may affect motivation and the presence of positive role models.	2.27	+	0.84	Sometimes
5. I make it difficult to cope academic stress or challenges due to the absence of my parents.	2.27	+	0.90	Sometimes
6. My parents are actively involved in my academic life.	2.39	+	0.93	Sometimes
7. I feel supported by my parents in my educational pursuits.	2.35	+	0.92	Sometimes
8. I believe parental involvement positively impacts my academic success.	2.45	+	0.93	Sometimes
9. I can discuss school-related matters with my parents.	2.35	+	0.94	Sometimes
10. I feel sense of encouragement from my parents regarding my school performance.	2.17	+	0.96	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.28	+	0.53	Sometimes

Note: 3.25–4.00, Always; 2.50–3.24, Often; 1.75–2.49, Sometimes; 1.00–1.74, Never

Table 12 displays the respondents' challenges in parental involvement as absentee parents. The result showed that the highest parental involvement in terms of lack of absentee parents was the statement "I feel sense of encouragement from my parents regarding my school performance" with weighted mean of "2.17" and standard deviation of "+0.96" with description of "sometimes". The result showed that a sense of encouragement from parents regarding school performance is a powerful motivator for learners.

The significant impact of parental encouragement on students' academic motivation, self-esteem, and ultimately, their school performance. Wang et al. underscored the importance of fostering positive parent-child relationships and providing supportive environments that promote student well-being and success according to the study of Wang (2021) on the relationship between parental encouragement and student school performance.

When parents express support, appreciation, and confidence in their children's abilities, it fosters a positive mindset and boosts self-esteem. This encouragement serves as a foundation for students to tackle academic challenges, persist in the face of setbacks, and strive for excellence. Moreover, parental encouragement creates a supportive home environment where students feel valued, understood, and empowered to reach their full potential. By nurturing a culture of encouragement, parents play a pivotal role in shaping their children's attitudes towards learning, fostering resilience, and promoting academic success.

The lowest result in terms of absentee parents was the statement "The absence of my parent figures may affect motivation and the presence of positive role models" with weighted mean of "2.27" with standard deviation of "+0.84" with description of "sometimes". The result showed that the absence of parental figures may not necessarily hinder an individual's motivation, especially if they have positive role models in their lives.

According to Chen, (2020) on a qualitative study investigating the influence of positive role models on learner motivation in hinterland regions where parent figures may be absent, the significant impact of positive role models, such as teachers, community leaders, and peers, in fostering student motivation and academic engagement.

The absence of parent figures may not significantly affect motivation and academic performance in learners in hinterland areas due to the presence of alternative support systems and resilient community dynamics. In these settings, extended family members, community elders, and teachers often step in to provide guidance and encouragement, ensuring that learners receive the necessary support to excel academically. This robust network of support helps mitigate the impact of parental absence on motivation and academic performance, allowing learners in hinterland areas to thrive despite challenging circumstances.

Furthermore, challenges in parental involvement due to absentee parents may not necessarily hinder academic performance when other support systems, such as teachers, mentors, or family members, are actively involved in the learner's life. While parental involvement is valuable, academic success can still be achieved through supportive relationships with other caregivers and role models. However, it's essential to acknowledge that parental involvement plays a significant role in shaping students' academic motivation, self-esteem, and overall well-being. Therefore, efforts to engage absentee parents and strengthen family-school partnerships remain vital in promoting equitable educational opportunities for all learners.

Table 13. *Challenges in Parental Involvement as to Broken Family*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My emotional strain resulting from a broken family may affect my concentration and emotional well-being which lead to mind disruption during class.	2.21	+	0.99	Sometimes
2. Ongoing conflict and stress related to the broken family situation can create distractions and anxiety and can loss focus on my academic.	2.12	+	0.90	Sometimes
3. Coping with the emotional toll of a broken family can be challenging and may affect my ability to manage stress and emotions.	2.13	+	0.88	Sometimes
4. Absence or reduced involvement of one parent may result in limited academic support and guidance.	2.27	+	0.90	Sometimes
5. Financial challenges stemming from a broken family may result in difficulty affording educational expenses.	2.22	+	0.87	Sometimes
6. I cannot concentrate on my studies because of family issues.	2.19	+	0.89	Sometimes
7. The breakdown of my parents' relationship has impacted my academic performance.	2.19	+	0.87	Sometimes
8. The changes in my family structure have affected my over-all well-being.	2.38	+	0.97	Sometimes
9. I believe that a stable family environment is essential for academic success.	2.30	+	0.93	Sometimes
10. I feel a sense of stability in my academic life despite the family changes.	2.22	+	0.54	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.22	+	0.87	Sometimes

Note: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Often; 1.75-2.49, Sometimes; 1.00-1.74, Never

Table 12 exhibits the respondents' challenges in parental involvement as broken family. The result showed that the highest parental involvement in terms of lack of broken family was the statement "My emotional strain resulting from a broken family may affect my concentration and emotional well-being which lead to mind disruption during class" with weighted mean of "2.21" and standard deviation of "+0.99" with description of "sometimes". The results showed that the emotional strain resulting from a broken family can have a profound impact on students' concentration and emotional well-being, often leading to disruptions during class.

On a qualitative study examining the impact of broken family structures on learner emotional well-being and concentration in educational settings by Wong (2021), highlighted the emotional strain experienced by students from broken families, which often led to difficulties in concentration and emotional regulation during class.

Students experiencing family breakdowns may grapple with feelings of sadness, anxiety, or confusion, which can impede their ability to focus on academic tasks and engage in classroom activities. Emotional distress may manifest as behavioral challenges, such as acting out, withdrawal, or difficulty regulating emotions, further disrupting the learning environment for both the student and their peers.

Addressing the emotional needs of students from broken families requires empathy, support, and access to counseling services to help them navigate their emotions, build resilience, and maintain focus on their academic pursuits despite the challenges they may face outside of school.

The lowest result in terms of broken family was the statement "I feel a sense of stability in my academic life despite the family changes" with weighted mean of "2.22" with standard deviation of "+0.54" with description of "sometimes". The findings showed that despite family changes, students can still cultivate a sense of stability in their academic lives through supportive school environments, consistent routines, and access to resources.

According to Gupta (2020) on a qualitative study examining the impact of family changes, such as divorce, remarriage, or relocation, on academic stability among students. Their research highlighted the destabilizing effects of family changes on students' sense of academic security and well-being.

Schools play a crucial role in providing a safe and stable space where students can focus on their education despite challenges at home. By fostering positive relationships with teachers, peers, and other supportive adults, students can find a sense of belonging and continuity in their academic journey.

Additionally, Challenges in parental involvement due to a broken family may not necessarily hinder academic performance, as learners can find support and motivation from other sources such as teachers, mentors, or extended family members. While parental involvement is important for academic success, resilient learners can thrive academically through alternative support systems.

However, it's essential to acknowledge that family dynamics play a significant role in shaping students' well-being and academic outcomes. Therefore, efforts to engage parents and caregivers, provide social-emotional support, and foster a supportive learning environment remain crucial in promoting academic success for all learners, regardless of family structure.

Problem 2: What is the academic performance of the learners during the 1st semester of the school year 2023-2024?Table 14. *Academic Performance*

<i>Performance Rating</i>	<i>Grading Scale</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Outstanding	90-100	37	21.0
Very Satisfactory	85-89	68	38.6
Satisfactory	80-84	63	35.8
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	8	4.5
Did not meet Expectations	Below 75	0	0
Total		176	100.0

Table 14 presents the academic performance of the respondents during the 1st semester of the School Year 2023-2024. The result showed that the highest performance rating falls under "Very Satisfactory" with frequency count of "37" and a percentage of "38.6%". This means that learners' performance ratings based on their challenges are categorized as "very satisfactory," it suggests that they have consistently met or exceeded expectations in overcoming obstacles or difficulties. This indicates a strong level of competence and proficiency in handling challenges within their learning context. It reflects an ability to adapt, problem-solve, and achieve desired outcomes effectively according to Chen (2021).

Overall, it signifies a high level of performance and capability in navigating and overcoming obstacles. Second, is the performance rating of "Satisfactory" with frequency count of "63" and a percentage of "35.8%". This implied that they have generally met the expected standards in addressing and overcoming obstacles. While they may have encountered some difficulties, they have been able to manage them adequately to achieve acceptable outcomes. However, there might be room for improvement in certain areas or situations where they could enhance their problem-solving skills or strategies to attain even better results. Overall, a "satisfactory" rating suggests a reasonable level of competence and effectiveness in dealing with challenges, although there may be areas for refinement or growth. Third, is the performance rating of "outstanding" with frequency count of "37" and a percentage of "21.0%". The result indicates an exceptional level of proficiency and effectiveness in overcoming obstacles. The learners have demonstrated exceptional problem-solving skills, resilience, and creativity in addressing challenges. They consistently surpass expectations, achieve remarkable results, and often serve as examples to others. Their ability to navigate challenges with excellence showcases their strong adaptability, determination, and resourcefulness (Gupta 2022).

Overall, an "outstanding" rating signifies exceptional competence and achievement in overcoming obstacles, setting a high standard for performance and inspiring others to follow suit.

Next, is the performance rating of "Fairly Satisfactory" with frequency count of "8" and a percentage of "4.5%" and the last was the performance rating of "Did not meet Expectations" with frequency count of "0" and a percentage of "0%". This implies that when learners' performance ratings based on their encountered challenges fall under "fairly satisfactory," it suggests that they have managed to address some obstacles adequately but may have struggled or encountered difficulties in certain areas. While they have shown some level of competence in overcoming challenges, there is still room for improvement to reach a more consistently satisfactory level of performance.

On the other hand, when learners' performance falls under "did not meet expectations," it indicates that they have not successfully addressed or overcome the challenges they encountered. This suggested a significant gap between the expected and actual performance levels, indicating areas where improvement is needed. It may be necessary for these learners to reassess their approaches, seek additional support or resources, and develop stronger problem-solving skills to effectively handle challenges in the future (Johnson (2021).

Overall, these results highlighted the varying degrees of proficiency among learners in navigating challenges, with opportunities for growth and development for those who have not met expectations.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between challenges encountered and the academic performance of the learners?

Table 15 displays the relationship between challenges encountered and the academic performance of the learners. The result showed that the respondents' academic performance had no significant relationship with their challenges encountered. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the challenges encountered and the academic performance of the learners, was not rejected.

The lack of significant relationship between respondents' academic performance and the challenges they encountered suggests a nuanced interplay of various factors influencing student success. It implies that while challenges are present, they may not always directly impact academic outcomes.

This could be attributed to factors such as individual resilience, access to resources, effective coping strategies, and intrinsic motivation, which may buffer the adverse effects of challenges on academic performance. Additionally, it underscored the complexity of student experiences, highlighting the need for a holistic understanding of factors contributing to academic success beyond just the challenges encountered.

Table 15. Relationship1 Respondents' Academic Performance and Challenges Encountered

Variables	Academic Performance		Remarks	Decision
	r - value	p-value		
Personal				
Affection	0.062	0.413	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Emotional	0.022	0.773	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Physical	0.093	0.219	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Environmental				
Social	0.037	0.629	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Natural Hazard	0.005	0.944	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Transportation	0.003	0.973	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Educational				
Teacher's Involvement	0.045	0.553	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Learning Resources	-0.006	0.939	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Parental Involvement				
Lack of Financial/Poverty	0.018	0.815	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Absentee Parents	0.071	0.350	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Broken Family	-0.067	0.719	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 1 – based on Pearson's r Correlation ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns - P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

Problem 4: Which of the challenges significantly affect the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 16 presents the variables that best predict respondents' academic performance. The respondents' academic performance was not affected by the challenges they encountered. This implied that no variables affect the respondents' academic performance.

Table 16. Variables that best predict Respondents' Academic Performance

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	84.670	2.207		38.369	0.000
Personal					
Affection	0.475	0.941	0.051	0.505	0.614
Emotional	-0.609	1.016	-0.066	-0.599	0.550
Physical	1.488	1.160	0.167	1.283	0.201
Environmental					
Social	-0.500	1.108	-0.058	-0.451	0.652
Natural Hazard	-0.135	0.929	-0.017	-0.145	0.885
Transportation	-0.281	0.911	-0.036	-0.308	0.758
Educational					
Teacher's Involvement	0.302	0.954	0.034	0.316	0.752
Learning Resources	-0.456	0.911	-0.053	-0.501	0.617
Parental Involvement					
Lack of Financial/Poverty	0.134	0.948	0.015	0.141	0.888
Absentee Parents	0.763	0.840	0.094	0.908	0.365
Broken Family	-0.683	0.824	-0.087	-0.829	0.409
	R = 0.162	R2 = 0.026	F = 0.401	Sig. = 0.954	

The R2 value of 0.026 implies that 2.6% of the variance in academic performance can be explained in the encountered challenges. Hence, 97.4% of the respondents' academic performance difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 0.401 with a corresponding p-value of 0.954. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' academic performance" was not rejected.

The finding that the challenges encountered by the respondents did not significantly impact their academic performance suggested a resilience or adaptive capacity within the student population. It implied that despite facing obstacles, these students were able to maintain or even excel in their academic endeavors. This underscored the importance of exploring factors such as coping mechanisms, support systems, and individual strengths that could contribute to academic success despite external challenges.

Problem 5: What action plan can be designed to be formulated based on the results of the study?

Rationale

Action plan served as a strategic roadmap outlining specific steps and objectives to achieve a set goal or address a particular issue. It provides clarity, direction, and accountability for individuals towards a common objective.

Through analyzing data and results of the study, this action plan addresses the challenges encountered in improving the academic performance of learners, aiming to identify key obstacles, implement targeted interventions, and drive measurable progress. This seeks to create a supportive learning environment that empowers learners to excel academically and reach their full potential.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis and findings derived from the study, the following conclusions are stipulated.

The study on the challenges encountered by senior high school learners and their academic performance, can be concluded that despite facing various obstacles, learners in hinterland schools demonstrated resilience in managing their academic performance. These learners exhibited the ability to navigate through challenges without significantly compromising their educational achievements or overall life situation.

This conclusion highlighted the remarkable adaptability and determination of learners in overcoming barriers to learning. It also suggested that the support systems in place, whether within the school environment or from external sources, are effective in assisting learners in mitigating the impact of challenges on their academic journey.

Furthermore, the resilience shown by students underscored the importance of recognizing and addressing the specific challenges faced by learners, particularly those in remote or disadvantaged areas. By understanding these challenges, educators can develop targeted interventions and support mechanisms to further enhance learners' academic success and overall well-being.

Overall, the study emphasized the importance of acknowledging the resilience and capabilities of learners in overcoming challenges, while also emphasizing the need for continued efforts to provide equitable access to education and support systems for all learners.

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